

Data Management Plan

Deliverable 1.3

WP1. Management and Coordination

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

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From March 2017 to May 2020

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
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Approvals

	Company
Author/s	CIRCE
Task Leader	CIRCE
WP Leader	CIRCE

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ABBREVIATIONS

API: Application Programming Interface
B&C: Biodegradable & Compostable
DMP: Data Management Plan
DOI: Digital Object Identifier
EU: European Union
FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
LCC: Life Cycle Cost
WP: Work Package

PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

CIRCE: Fundación CIRCE – Research Centre for Energy Resources and Consumption
AITIIP: Fundación AITIIP
NOVAMONT: NOVAMONT SPA
MATER: MATER-BIOTECH SPA
MBP: MATER-BIOPOLYMER SRL
BUMAGA BV: BUMAGA BV
TECNOPACKAGING: NUEVAS TECNOLOGIAS PARA EL DESARROLLO DE PACKAGING Y PRODUCTOS AGROALIMENTARIOS CON COMPONENTE PLASTICA SL
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GRUPO SADA: GRUPO SADA P A SA
SAPONIA D.D.: SAPONIA KEMIJSKA, PREHRAMBENA I FARMACEUTSKA INDUSTRIJA D.D.
FATER: Fater S.p.A.
CRF: CENTRO RICERCHE FIAT SCPA
UNE: ASOCIACION ESPAÑOLA DE NORMALIZACION
RINA: RINA CONSULTING – D'APPOLONIA SPA
EKODENGE: EKODENGE MUHENDISLIK MIMARLIK DANISMANLIK TICARET ANONIM SIRKETI
ECOEMBES: ECOEMBALAJES ESPANA, S.A.
CITY OF RIJEKA: GRAD RIJEKA-GRADSKO VIJECE
KARTALMUN: KARTAL BELEDIYE BASKANLIGI
CALAF IND: CALAF TECHNIQUES INDUSTRIALS SL
OCU EDICIONES: OCU EDICIONES SA
ICLEI EURO: ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)
PLASTIPOLIS: PLASTIPOLIS

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

As part of Horizon 2020, the CIRCE-PACK project participates in a pilot action on open research data. The aim is to provide indications as to what kind of data the project will collect, how the data will be preserved and which sharing policies will be adopted towards making these data readily available to the research community.

Data management is an important aspect of European projects as it ensures long-term preservation and accessibility of data during the project and after the project has ended. The Data Management Plan (DMP) also outlines how the data are handled during the lifetime of the project and after it has been completed. In addition, the DMP seeks to reduce the risk of data loss or other threats that could render the data illegible or unusable.

In particular, CIRCE-PACK DMP details what kind of research data will be created during the project's lifespan, prescribes how these data will be made available - and thus re-usable and verifiable - by the larger research community and describes dataset generated within each Work Package (WP). The project's efforts in the area of open research data are outlined giving particular attention to the following issues:

- The types of open and non-open data that will be generated or collected by the consortium, via experimental campaigns and research, during the project's lifespan;
- The technologies and infrastructures that will be used to securely preserve the data long-term;
- The standards used to encode the data;
- The data exploitation plans;
- The sharing/access policies applied to each dataset.

The content of this document is built upon project partners input. A short questionnaire, outlining the DMP's objectives and stating the required information in a structured manner, was developed by CIRCE and shared among the partners. The compiled answers are integrated in this deliverable.

The present DMP is also the final version showing the final state of consortium's agreements regarding data management, exploitation and protection of rights and results.

For each partner involved in the collection or generation of research data a short technical description is given stating the context in which the data has been created. The different datasets are identified by project-wide unique identifiers and categorized through additional meta-data such as, for example, the sharing policy attached to it.

The considered storage facilities are outlined and tutorials were provided for their use (submitting and retrieving the research data).

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INTRODUCTION

Data management is an important aspect of European projects as it ensures long-term preservation and accessibility of data during the project and once the project has ended. The DMP also outlines how the data is handled during project lifetime and after it has been completed. In addition, the DMP seeks to reduce the risk of data loss or other threats that could render the data illegible or unusable.

CIRC-PACK Data Management Plan (DMP) details the data the project has generated and managed, following what methodology and standards. It also explains how the data is made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it is curated and preserved with respect to the FAIR principles and the EU GDPR. The signed Consortium Agreement defined the ownership of prior and post key knowledge (IPR, data etc.) of all involved beneficiaries.

The Data Management Plan has been a living document that was regularly updated to support the data management lifecycle for all data that is collected, processed or generated by the project.

The first version of DMP established the measures for promoting the findings during CIRC-PACK's lifecycle and set the procedures for the sharing of project data. Addressing FAIR principle for research data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) CIRC-PACK DMP considered:

- Dataset reference and name
- Data set description
- Standards and metadata
- Data sharing and handling during and after the end of the project
- Archiving and preservation (including after the end of the project)

This final version of DMP includes all the generated dataset, sorted by WP, explaining their nature, security and storage location.

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1 DATA SUMMARY

This section gives an overview of project scope in order to clarify the relation between it and the data generated, collected and/or processed in the project.

1.1 Purpose of the dataset

CIRC-PACK project aims at developing a more sustainable, efficient, competitive, less fossil fuel dependence, integrated and interconnected plastic packaging value chain. To this end, three case studies worked in developing, testing and validating better system-wide economic and environmental outcomes by i) decoupling the chain from fossil feed stocks, (ii) reducing the negative environmental impact of plastic packaging; and (iii) creating an effective after-use plastics economy.

Demo cases work was supported by non-technological analysis (involving end users) and advanced methodological analysis (including circular economy and industrial symbiosis principles) triggering a broadly deployment of the tested solutions. Within CIRC-PACK project biodegradable and compostable plastics (based on alternative biobased raw materials) were developed, as well as multilayer and multimaterial packaging having a great impact in the packaging footprint and, consequently, playing an important role in plastic value chain.

In addition, in order to enhance the replicability of the proposed innovations, sustainable business models were applied, thus activating a self-spreading principle that open the door for the wide implementation of CIRC-PACK principles.

The overall outcome of the project facilitates the transition from the current linear plastic packaging value chain to circular economy principles.

Given above mentioned activities, main project dataset are, on the one hand, experimental data generated from the demo cases (i.e. WP3, WP4 and WP5) and, on the other hand, observational and end user data collected from solution testing and business models development (i.e. WP7). This data, along with other derived data from circularity improvement evaluation (i.e. WP2), cross-sectorial validation (i.e. WP6) and communication and dissemination activities (i.e. WP8), are structured into information and uploaded to CIRC-PACK main storage system (EMDESK). Additionally, other storage platforms were used, depending on the nature or purpose of the data. Compilation and analysis of this information resulted in knowledge that was disseminated as reports, press releases or scientific articles, for instance, accessible to different stakeholders. Furthermore, and according to what is explained in project Grant Agreement (Article 29.3), third parties are able to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate data and information generated or derived throughout the project, according to CIRC-PACK's ethics, privacy and data protection requirements.

1.2 Types of data

As stated in the first version of DMP the dataset categories managed in CIRC-PACK were:

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- **End-user personal data:** During baseline definition and preliminary assessment of packaging value chain, surveys were implemented in different countries in order to identify public perception and expectations about plastics and plastic packaging value chain, as well as to collect interesting info to be considered during project development regarding products design, waste management measures and dissemination activities. Besides, the exploitation and commercialization of knowledge and technical results achieved were also addressed.

This dataset is private and was managed only by the organization hosting the Data Repository where it is allocated. This collection was not shared unless the data were previously anonymized to remove any possible personal link. In those cases where data is shared this process was according to European regulation and requesting user's permission for doing it. Data protection and privacy in conjunction with market surveys.

- **Processes information of stages involved in demo cases:** Processes information was required during demo cases execution and to carry out Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Cost analysis (LCA/LCC) of plastic packaging value chain (before and after the implementation of project innovations). These analyses considered data such as flow diagrams, materials (input and output), energy consumption, transport of materials, storage conditions, raw materials, materials sorting, waste management, assets value and lifespan, investment and turnover, etc. Certain datasets cannot be shared (or restrictions are needed) so, legal and contractual reasons are explained in those cases.
- **Sensor data:** this collection comprises all information collected from sensors involved in waste sorting facilities, packaging sorting or recycled material tests. Although at the beginning of the project this type of data was defined as public (since it was not planned to identify any person), finally it is not public since it includes confidential data from involved partners.
- **Derived data:** this comprises the result of applying data analytics techniques to the data steaming from sensors as well as compiled data from other sources or demo cases. Although at the beginning of the project this collection was considered as public (since it was not planned to identify any person), finally its nature depends on the collected data.
- **Project management data:** this new data type is used for internal management of the project and its partners. It includes, for instance, minutes, contact list or communication and dissemination data.

Regarding the nature of the data, in order to fulfil the required security and privacy requirements in this project, which are set by the Data Protection Directive (Directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data), the project assumes the differentiation set in this Directive between Personal and No Personal data. Data are considered as personal data "when someone is able to link the information to a person, even if the person holding the data cannot make this link". Any data susceptible of being considered as Personal Data will be managed according to this Directive.

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2 STANDARDS AND METADATA

Reports, process data, surveys, databases, data collected in public events or statistics used spreadsheets, text, and presentation formats to be easily accessible by third parties and researchers who want to further use or reproduce the data. Nevertheless, raw data may not be possible to store under these formats. In these cases, or when data requires to be saved in other specific formats, datasets were stored according to partners' criteria.

Data standards used within CIRCE-PACK project have been:

- **Spreadsheets:** Many beneficiaries store information in spreadsheets, for example Microsoft Excel. This data can be used immediately, given the information descriptions in the rows and columns. In some cases, there are macros and formulas in spreadsheets, which may be somewhat more cumbersome to handle. Consequently, it is advisable to document such calculations within the spreadsheet, in order to make them easier to read.
- **Comma Separated Values (CSV):** CSV files are a very useful standard because it is compact and thus suitable to transfer large sets of data with the same structure. However, the format is so limited that data can often be useless without documentation since it can be almost impossible to guess the significance of the different columns. It is therefore particularly important for the comma separated values formats that documentation or meta-information of the individual fields is provided and is sufficient and accurate.
- **Text Documents:** Formats like DOCX, RTF, ODF, or PDF are appropriate for certain kinds of documents, e.g., scientific journals, deliverables, reports, etc. Templates have been used whenever possible, so that project image was communicated and displayed data could be re-used.
- **Presentation (.ppt):** PPT is a file extension for a presentation file format used by Microsoft PowerPoint. The popular presentation software is commonly used for project slide shows.
- **Image or photo formats (.jpg, .png):** Image file formats are composed of digital data in one of these formats that can be rasterized for use on a computer display or printer. An image file format may store data in uncompressed, compressed, or vector formats.
- **Audio formats (.wav, .mp3, .ogg):** An audio file format is a file format for storing digital audio data on a computer system. The audio coding format can be uncompressed or compressed to reduce the file size.
- **Video formats (.avi, Quicktime Movie, Windows Media Video):** A video file format is a type of file format for storing digital video data on a computer system. A video file normally consists of a container, containing video data in a video coding format, alongside audio data in an audio coding format. The container can also contain synchronization information, subtitles, and metadata such as title.

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- Quantitative data analysis will be stored in SAV file format (used by SPSS) from which data can be extracted using the open source spread Perl script.

These file formats have been chosen because they are accepted standards and in widespread use. Files will be converted to open file formats where possible for long-term storage.

Metadata will be comprised of two formats:

- Contextual information about the data in a text-based document
- ISO 19115 standard metadata in an xml file.

These two metadata formats were chosen to provide a full explanation of the data (text format) and to ensure compatibility with international standards (xml format).

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3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

CIRCE was responsible for data management in CIRC-PACK project.

Costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

Resources for long-term preservation, associated costs and potential value, as well as how data are kept beyond the project and how long, were discussed by the whole consortium during General Assembly meetings.

As stated above, coordination team (CIRCE) is responsible for ensuring proper management and processing of all data in the project, complying with the EU data protection regulations. Moreover, the coordination team is in charge of uploading the deliverables to the Funding & Tenders Portal and to place a copy on project intranet (EMDESK). The public deliverables as well as other types of public data were also uploaded by the coordinator to the Zenodo Platform.

The responsibilities of project members were:

- Regular update and classification of the data collected and generated within CIRC-PACK project
- Implementing and respecting 1st version of Data Management Plan (D1.2)

After project ending, all resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP allocated resources. No additional costs were spent or are foreseen for generating dataset according to FAIR principle.

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4 DATA SHARING, ACCESS AND PRESERVATION

CIRC-PACK is a European project where 22 partners took part, hence a large amount of data has been generated. To manage such quantities of data and allow the partners (and other researchers) to share them with each other, suitable storage media were used to comply with European privacy legislation.

All possible datasets were stored in project main storage system: CIRC-PACK intranet, i.e. EMDESK. This platform was the main system for storage of active research and project management data. Due to some datasets nature (e.g. a dataset that contains sensitive personal data, sensor measures...), these may use additional offline or online storage systems.

The digital data created by the project were diversely organized depending on sharing policies. For both open and non-open data, the aim is to preserve the data and make it readily available to the interested parties for the whole duration of the project and beyond. To this end, Zenodo was used as the main platform for long-term preservation of results and research data when confidentiality allows. Additional platforms, such as EMDESK or CIRC-PACK website were used to publish and disseminate data, along with publications in scientific journals, according to the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.1).

4.1 Storage systems

The storage systems will include mainly - but not only - the following platforms:

4.1.1 CIRC-PACK intranet

The **non-open research data** were archived and stored long-term in the EMDESK portal administered by CIRCE. This platform was employed to coordinate project activities and to store all the digital material connected to CIRC-PACK. EMDESK is furthermore GDPR compliant.

If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need restrictions), legal and contractual reasons will be explained.

Access to CIRC-PACK intranet is limited to consortium members and the coordination team.

The consortium stored as much project data as possible on the project's intranet, including:

- Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement;
- Project reports and deliverables (public and confidential);
- Project contact list;
- All communication and dissemination-related material;
- Project templates;
- Consent forms signed by participants;
- Minutes of meetings;
- Pictures taken during conferences, workshops and seminars;

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4.1.2 Zenodo platform

The **open research data** were archived on the Zenodo platform (<http://www.zenodo.org>). Zenodo is an EU-backed portal based on the well-established GIT version control system (<https://git-scm.com>) and the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) system (<http://www.doi.org>).

The portal's aims are inspired by the same principles that the EU sets for the pilot; Zenodo represents thus a very suitable and natural choice in this context.

The repository services offered by Zenodo are free of charge and enable peers to share and preserve research data and other research outputs in any size and format: datasets, images, presentations, publications and software. The digital data and the associated meta-data are preserved through well-established practices such as mirroring and periodic backups.

Each uploaded dataset is assigned a unique DOI rendering each submission uniquely identifiable and thus traceable and referenceable.

4.1.3 On premises - Partners internal facilities/servers

Some of project datasets were stored at the premises of the owning consortium partners, including software, tools, measurements... It is partners' responsibility to ensure that such data complies with the GDPR principles and respect the requirements presented in the Ethics Deliverables (D9.1, D9.2, D9.3, D9.4 and D9.5).

4.2 Sharing systems

The sharing systems will include mainly - but not only - the following platforms:

4.2.1 CIRC-PACK website

The consortium disseminated all applicable data on CIRC-PACK's website (<https://circpack.eu/>), which was regularly updated by the WP8 Leader (ICLEI EURO). The website, setup and maintained by ICLEI, has been a front-end platform to disseminate knowledge and public data developed within CIRC-PACK.

4.2.2 CIRC-PACK European platforms

Regarding European platforms, the project shared allowed data and results, on the one hand, via **CORDIS platform** (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730423>) and, on the other hand via **Horizon Results platform** (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>)

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5 ETHIC ASPECTS

5.1 Personal data collected through the interviews and surveys imported from Turkey to the EU partners / exported from EU partners to Turkey

Personal data of users were collected during the social acceptance and participation in eco-design. Regarding personal data from Kartal (non-EU country), KARTALMUN collected the information at local level through digital media (tablets, computers, etc.). These data were collected and included in an excel file by an external Turkish entity. This excel file showed only aggregated data (not identity data) and was analysed and processed by OCU EDICIONES, together with the rest of countries information. All surveys were processed anonymously and no personal data was exported from EU partners to a non-EU country.

Procedures to be implemented in Turkey to manage personal data, were established by KARTALMUN and the external entity, according to national regulation.

5.2 Collection, storage and protection of personal data

EU countries surveys were based on a combined self-administered postal and online sampling and data collection approach. Necessary measures were taken for guaranteeing optimal anonymization of collected, analysed and stored data. Respondents were comprehensibly informed about it and, whenever necessary, survey respondents were requested for their explicit consent (e.g. in case of follow-up/second-layer contacts & questionnaires).

Collected data were used exclusively within the context and for the purpose of the CIRC-PACK project. No data was transmitted to any person, company or organization not being involved on the CIRC-PACK project. Collected data was not used for commercial purposes.

All personal data was collected, stored and destructed only with and accordingly to the consent of the personal data holder.

The research complied with:

- ethical principles
- applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC).

Data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction were carried out through the project intranet system (EMDESK).

Interviewees/beneficiaries/recipients were informed about data security, anonymity and use of data as well as asked for accordance. Participation happens on a voluntary basis.

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6 LIST OF THE DATA-SETS

6.1 WP1 - Management and Coordination

6.1.1 Project contact list

DMP criteria		Project contact list
Data summary		Project management data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	<p>The database contains name, organisation and contact details for all project partners.</p> <p>This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (excel file '.xls.') containing following fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partner short name • Country • Name and surname • Position in the organization • Email • Phone number • Skype ID • Role within the project
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	This dataset is not publicly available. Contact list is available to beneficiaries through project intranet (EMDESK)
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	N/A
	Increase data RE-USE	This dataset can be accessed and re-used by partners by logging in project intranet (EMDESK)
Allocations of resources		<p>CIRCE is responsible for dataset management and for ensuring that contact list is continuously updated.</p> <p>Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP1 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.</p>
Data security		<p>Non-open Research Data.</p> <p>The data have been collected for internal use in the project and is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project ending.</p>
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		Uploaded into project intranet (EMDESK)

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.1.2 Minutes of Meeting

DMP criteria		Minutes of Meeting
Data summary		Project management data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	<p>The database contains the Minutes of Meeting held during the project. The information of this dataset can be found different deliverables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1.4 "Kick off meeting minutes" • D1.5 "First Steering Committee meeting minutes" • D1.6 "First General Assembly meeting minutes and second Steering Committee meeting minutes" • D1.7 "Third Steering Committee meeting minutes" • D1.8 "Second General Assembly meeting minutes and fourth Steering Committee meeting minutes" • D1.9 "Fifth Steering Committee meeting minutes" • D1.10 "Third and last General Assembly meeting minutes, sixth and last steering committee meeting minutes"
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	<p>This dataset is confidential.</p> <p>Minutes of Meetings are available to beneficiaries through project intranet (EMDESK)</p>
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	N/A
	Increase data RE-USE	This dataset can be accessed and re-used by partners by logging in project intranet (EMDESK)
Allocations of resources		<p>CIRCE is responsible for dataset management and for ensuring that contact list is continuously updated.</p> <p>Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP1 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.</p>
Data security		<p>Non-open Research Data.</p> <p>The data have been collected for internal use in the project and is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project ending.</p>
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		Uploaded into project intranet (EMDESK)

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.2 WP2 - Baseline and circularity improvement evaluation methodologies

6.2.1 LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to fossil-based plastic and bioplastic used to manufacture shampoo bottles

DMP criteria		LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to fossil-based plastic and bioplastic used to manufacture shampoo bottles
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Data related to shampoo bottles made by plastic-based plastic is available in D2.3 and D2.6. Data related to the same bottles but made by bioplastic is available in D2.4
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	On the one hand, D2.6 is a public report and can be found in https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730423/results . On the other hand, D2.3 and D2.4 are confidential reports and are available in the participant portal of the EC but only for members of the project consortium
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This data might be used to improve the sustainability of shampoo plastic bottles since it includes the analysis made from different perspectives (environmental, economic, social and circularity).
	Increase data RE-USE	Data related to fossil-based plastic bottles can be used to establish a baseline to compare any other improvements made in the design of conventional shampoo bottles, as well as for comparative purposes. Data related to bioplastic bottles can be used to communicate the impacts caused by the project implementation and to highlight the benefits of using sustainable plastics.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Data related to conventional plastic bottles: open research data. Data related to the biobased shampoo bottles: Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.2.2 LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to fossil-based plastic and bioplastic used to manufacture food trays

DMP criteria		LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to fossil-based plastic and bioplastic used to manufacture food trays
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Data related to food trays made by plastic-based plastic is available in D2.3 and D2.6. Data related to the same trays but made by bioplastic is available in D2.4
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	On the one hand, D2.6 is a public report and can be found in https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730423/results . On the other hand, D2.3 and D2.4 are confidential reports and are available in the participant portal of the EC but only for members of the project consortium
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This data might be used to improve the sustainability of plastic food trays since it includes the analysis made from different perspectives (environmental, economic, social and circularity).
	Increase data RE-USE	Data related to fossil-based plastic trays can be used to establish a baseline to compare any other improvements made in the design of conventional trays, as well as for comparative purposes. Data related to bioplastic trays can be used to communicate the impacts caused by the project implementation and to highlight the benefits of using sustainable plastics.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Data related to conventional plastic trays: open research data. Data related to the biobased trays: Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.2.3 LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to fossil-based plastic and bioplastic used to manufacture shopping bags

DMP criteria		LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to fossil-based plastic and bioplastic used to manufacture shopping bags
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Data related to shopping bags made by plastic-based plastic is available in D2.3 and D2.6. Data related to the same bags but made by bioplastic is available in D2.4
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	On the one hand, D2.6 is a public report and can be found in https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730423/results . On the other hand, D2.3 and D2.4 are confidential reports and are available in the participant portal of the EC but only for members of the project consortium
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This data might be used to improve the sustainability of plastic shopping bags since it includes the analysis made from different perspectives (environmental, economic, social and circularity).
	Increase data RE-USE	Data related to fossil-based plastic bags can be used to establish a baseline to compare any other improvements made in the design of conventional bags, as well as for comparative purposes. Data related to bioplastic bags can be used to communicate the impacts caused by the project implementation and to highlight the benefits of using sustainable plastics.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Data related to conventional plastic bags: open research data. Data related to the biobased bags: Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.2.4 LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to fossil-based plastic and bioplastic used to manufacture coffee capsules

DMP criteria		LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to fossil-based plastic and bioplastic used to manufacture coffee capsules
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Data related to coffee capsules made by plastic-based plastic is available in D2.3 and D2.6. Data related to the same capsules but made by bioplastic is available in D2.4
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	On the one hand, D2.6 is a public report and can be found in https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730423/results . On the other hand, D2.3 and D2.4 are confidential reports and are available in the participant portal of the EC but only for members of the project consortium
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This data might be used to improve the sustainability of coffee capsules since it includes the analysis made from different perspectives (environmental, economic, social and circularity).
	Increase data RE-USE	Data related to fossil-based plastic capsules can be used to establish a baseline to compare any other improvements made in the design of conventional capsules, as well as for comparative purposes. Data related to bioplastic capsules can be used to communicate the impacts caused by the project implementation and to highlight the benefits of using sustainable plastics.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Data related to conventional plastic capsules: open research data. Data related to the biobased capsules: Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.2.5 LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to PE-laminated and biobased dispersion coating material used to manufacture powder detergent boxes

DMP criteria		LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to PE-laminated and biobased dispersion coating material used to manufacture powder detergent boxes
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Data related to powder detergent boxes made by a PE-layered material is available in D2.3 and D2.6. Data related to the same boxes but made by a biobased dispersion coating material is available in D2.4
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	On the one hand, D2.6 is a public report and can be found in https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730423/results . On the other hand, D2.3 and D2.4 are confidential reports and are available in the participant portal of the EC but only for members of the project consortium
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This data might be used to improve the sustainability of powder detergent boxes since it includes the analysis made from different perspectives (environmental, economic, social and circularity).
	Increase data RE-USE	Data related to PE-layered powder detergent boxes can be used to establish a baseline to compare any other improvements made in the design of conventional boxes, as well as for comparative purposes. Data related to the improved boxes can be used to communicate the impacts caused by the project implementation and to highlight the benefits of using sustainable and innovative materials.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Data related to conventional powder detergent boxes: open research data. Data related to the CIRC-PACK detergent boxes: Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.2.6 LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to recycling process carried out in automotive sector

DMP criteria		LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to recycling process carried out in automotive sector
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Data related to energy and material resources consumption necessary to manufacture air ducts and bumpers by a conventional process is available in D2.3 and D2.6. Data related to the same processes but after implementing the CIRC-PACK innovations is available in D2.4
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	On the one hand, D2.6 is a public report and can be found in https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730423/results . On the other hand, D2.3 and D2.4 are confidential reports and are available in the participant portal of the EC but only for members of the project consortium
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This data might be used to continue improving the sustainability of the automotive sector manufacturing processes since it includes the analysis made from different perspectives (environmental, economic, social and circularity).
	Increase data RE-USE	Results can be used to establish a baseline to compare any other improvements made in these manufacturing processes, as well as for comparative purpose. Besides, they can be used to communicate the impacts caused by the project implementation and to highlight the benefits of using sustainable and innovative materials.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Data related to conventional manufacturing processes: open research data. Data related to the CIRC-PACK processes: Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.2.7 LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to recycling and re-design of Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHPs)

DMP criteria		LCA/LCC/S-LCA/Circularity results related to recycling and re-design of Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHPs)
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Data related to energy and material resources consumption necessary to manufacture conventional AHP products (diapers' box, secondary packaging of diapers and mini pallets), is available in D2.3 and D2.6. Data related to the same processes but after implementing the CIRC-PACK innovations is available in D2.4
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	On the one hand, D2.6 is a public report and can be found in https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730423/results . On the other hand, D2.3 and D2.4 are confidential reports and are available in the participant portal of the EC but only for members of the project consortium
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This data might be used to continue improving the sustainability of the AHPs value chain since it includes the analysis made from different perspectives (environmental, economic, social and circularity).
	Increase data RE-USE	Results can be used to establish a baseline to compare any other improvements made in the AHP manufacturing processes, as well as for comparative purpose. Besides, they can be used to communicate the impacts caused by the project implementation and to highlight the benefits of using sustainable and innovative materials.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Data related to conventional manufacturing processes: open research data. Data related to the CIRC-PACK processes: Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRCE-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.2.8 Development of an interactive and dynamic virtual map for packaging sector

DMP criteria		Development of an interactive and dynamic virtual map for packaging sector
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This virtual map is based on a tool available online which aims at providing some recommendations about how to improve the sustainability of different packaging solutions, and how to increase their circularity and recyclability.
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	The tool is available through the following link: https://circpack.fcirce.es/login It is a public deliverable, so anyone can use it.
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This data might be used as first evaluation to improve the sustainability of a plastic or cardboard packaging.
	Increase data RE-USE	Once defined the properties of a specific packaging, the tool provides a recyclability check, which includes a spider diagram showing which recyclability criteria is achieved by the packaging that it is being analysing. For those criteria that are not achieved, the tool provides some recommendations to achieve its sustainability. Depending on the number of criteria achieved, a scoring between A and F is given.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.3 WP3 - Demo Case A. Decoupling plastics from fossil feedstock by using alternative renewable feedstock.

6.3.1 1,4 bio-BDO production from renewable sugars

DMP criteria		1,4 bio-BDO production from renewable sugars
Data summary		Processes information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	<p>All the data, flow diagrams, raw materials, intermediates and final products properties, feasibility study for 1,4 bio-BDO plant configuration, shared are reported in D3.1 "Report on 1.4 BDO production and THF recovery (using sugars from AHP cellulose waste)".</p> <p>Data on this value chain are also shared for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.1 "Preliminary market analysis", • D7.2 "Final market analysis", • D7.3 "Guidelines for the uptake of ETV of CIRC-PACK processes", • D7.5 "Business analysis and business models for the development of the systems, Business Plan", • D7.8 "Final Exploitation Plan", • D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders" <p>Data for LCA, LCC, LCA-S are reported in D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain".</p>
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	<p>This dataset is accessible in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain" • D3.1 Report on 1.4 BDO production and THF recovery (using sugars from AHP cellulose waste), • D7.1 "Preliminary market analysis", • D7.2 "Final market analysis", • D7.3 "Guidelines for the uptake of ETV of CIRC-PACK processes", • D7.5 "Business analysis and business models for the development of the systems, Business Plan", • D7.8 "Final Exploitation Plan", • D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders" <p>All mentioned deliverables are confidential.</p>
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	Results represent knowledge for investigating the 1,4 bio-BDO production from other kinds of renewable sugars

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	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-Open research data. Raw data files are confidential and they are stored at Novamont and MATER facilities
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.3.2 Bio-THF recovery from wastewater of polymerization process

DMP criteria		Bio-THF recovery from wastewater of polymerization process
Data summary		Processes information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	<p>All the data, flow diagrams, raw materials, intermediates and final products properties, results of trials at large scale shared are reported in D3.1 "Report on 1.4 BDO production and THF recovery (using sugars from AHP cellulose waste)" Data on this value chain are shared also for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain", • D7.1 "Preliminary market analysis", • D7.2 "Final market analysis", • D7.3 "Guidelines for the uptake of ETV of CIRC-PACK processes", • D7.5 "Business analysis and business models for the development of the systems, Business Plan", • D7.8 "Final Exploitation Plan", • D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders"
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	<p>This dataset is accessible in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain" • D3.1 Report on 1.4 BDO production and THF recovery (using sugars from AHP cellulose waste), • D7.1 "Preliminary market analysis", • D7.2 "Final market analysis", • D7.3 "Guidelines for the uptake of ETV of CIRC-PACK processes", • D7.5 "Business analysis and business models for the development of the systems, Business Plan", • D7.8 "Final Exploitation Plan",

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders" <p>All mentioned deliverables are confidential.</p>
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	N/A
	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.	
Data security	Non-Open research data. Raw data files are confidential and they are stored at Novamont and MBP facilities	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)	
Other	N/A	

6.3.3 Composition, characterization and safety sheet of new developed biopolyester matrix and biomaterial formulations

DMP criteria	Composition, characterization and safety sheet of new developed biopolyester matrix and biomaterial formulations
Data summary	Processes information of stages involved in demo cases

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	<p>All the process data, flow diagrams, composition and characterization of biopolyesters matrix, composition, characterization and safety sheet of biomaterial formulations, results of test at pilot and large scale for the preparation of biopolyesters and biomaterials are reported in D3.3 "Report on new developed biopolymer blends and formulations (composition, characterization and safety sheet)"</p> <p>Data was shared also for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.1 "Preliminary market analysis", • D7.2 "Final market analysis", • D7.3 "Guidelines for the uptake of ETV of CIRC-PACK processes", • D7.5 "Business analysis and business models for the development of the systems, Business Plan", • D7.8 "Final Exploitation Plan", • D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders" <p>Data for LCA, LCC, LCA-S shared are reported in D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain".</p> <p>Data shared for biomaterials formulation developed for shampoo bottle and food tray application are reported in D3.2 "Report on improved Biomaterials for packaging applications"</p>
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	<p>This dataset is accessible in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain" • D3.2 "Report on improved Biomaterials for packaging applications", • D3.3 "Report on new developed biopolymer blends and formulations (composition, characterization and safety sheet)", • D7.1 "Preliminary market analysis", • D7.2 "Final market analysis", • D7.3 "Guidelines for the uptake of ETV of CIRC-PACK processes", • D7.5 "Business analysis and business models for the development of the systems, Business Plan", • D7.8 "Final Exploitation Plan", • D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders" <p>All mentioned deliverables are confidential.</p>

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

	Making data INTEROPERABLE	N/A
	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.	
Data security	Non-Open research data. Raw data files are confidential and they are stored at Novamont and MBP facilities	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)	
Other	N/A	

6.3.4 Validation of biomaterial formulation developed in coffee capsule application

DMP criteria		Validation of biomaterial formulation developed in coffee capsule application
Data summary		Processes information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	<p>All the process data, flow diagrams, composition and characterization of biopolyesters matrix, composition, characterization and safety sheet of biomaterial formulations, results of test at pilot and large scale for the preparation of biopolyesters and biomaterials for coffee capsule application are reported in D3.3 "Report on new developed biopolymer blends and formulations (composition, characterization and safety sheet)".</p> <p>Data was shared also for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.1 "Preliminary market analysis", • D7.2 "Final market analysis", • D7.3 "Guidelines for the uptake of ETV of CIRC-PACK processes", • D7.5 "Business analysis and business models for the development of the systems, Business Plan", • D7.8 "Final Exploitation Plan", • D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders" <p>Data for LCA, LCC, LCA-S shared are reported in D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain".</p>

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	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	<p>This dataset is accessible in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain" • D3.3 "Report on new developed biopolymer blends and formulations (composition, characterization and safety sheet)", • D7.1 "Preliminary market analysis", • D7.2 "Final market analysis", • D7.3 "Guidelines for the uptake of ETV of CIRC-PACK processes", • D7.5 "Business analysis and business models for the development of the systems, Business Plan", • D7.8 "Final Exploitation Plan", • D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders" <p>All mentioned deliverables are confidential.</p>
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	N/A
	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-Open research data. Raw data files are confidential and they are stored at Novamont and MBP facilities
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.3.5 Characterization of regenerated biomaterial from mechanical recycling of B&C process scraps

DMP criteria		Characterization of regenerated biomaterial from mechanical recycling of B&C process scraps
Data summary		Processes information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	All the process data, flow diagrams, composition and characterization of scraps, results of characterization tests on regenerated biomaterial are reported in D3.4 "Report on sorting and recyclability of new Biomaterials and Biopackaging, adaptation of current recycling protocols". Data for LCA, LCC, LCA-S are reported in D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain"

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	<p>This dataset is accessible in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D3.4 "Report on sorting and recyclability of new Biomaterials and Biopackaging, adaptation of current recycling protocols" • D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain" <p>All mentioned deliverables are confidential.</p>
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	N/A
	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-Open research data. Raw data files are confidential and they are stored at Novamont.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.3.6 Recycling process and recyclability of the new biomaterials

DMP criteria		Recycling process and recyclability of the new biomaterials
Data summary		Process information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Recycling methodology and processing information, materials (input, output, raw materials), processing parameters and settings, energy consumption, description of the process provided in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.1 "Report on the recycling methodology for packaging sector, possible adaptations and upgrade of the technology" • D3.4 "Report on sorting and recyclability of the new biomaterials and biopackaging, adaptation of current recycling protocols" • D7.5 "Business model and plan" • D7.8 "Final exploitation plan" • D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain" • CAPEX-OPEX LIST and Inventory baseline
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.	
Data security	Non-open research data	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)	
Other	N/A	

6.3.7 Manufacturing of films and bags

DMP criteria		Manufacturing of films and bags
Data summary		Process information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Processing information, materials (input, output, raw materials), processing parameters and settings, energy consumption shared in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D3.4 "Report on sorting and recyclability of the new biomaterials and biopackaging, adaptation of current recycling protocols", • D2.4 "Improved-state CIRC-PACK value chain", • CAPEX-OPEX LIST and Inventory baseline
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	N/A
	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.	
Data security	Non-open research data	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)	
Other	N/A	

6.3.8 Biomaterial extrusion process parameters

DMP criteria		Biomaterial extrusion process parameters
Data summary		Processes information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	All the data are reported in D3.2 "Report on improved Biomaterials for packaging applications"
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	Extrusion process data is only available during 72h, after that the data is deleted. So, no data gathered from the sensors is available. However, data are reported in D3.2 "Report on improved Biomaterials for packaging applications" which is confidential.

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

	Making data INTEROPERABLE	Extrusion process data is only available during 72h, after that the data is deleted. So, no data gathered from the sensors is available
	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.3.9 Biomaterial thermoforming process parameters

DMP criteria		Biomaterial thermoforming process parameters
Data summary		Processes information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	All the data are reported in D3.4 "Report on sorting and recyclability of new Biomaterials and Biopackaging, adaptation of current recycling protocols"
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	This dataset is accessible in D3.4 "Report on sorting and recyclability of new Biomaterials and Biopackaging, adaptation of current recycling protocols" which is confidential
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	It is possible to use this data as an approximation to process similar materials (prior agreement of partner Novamont is compulsory)
	Increase data RE-USE	N/A
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.3.10 Packaging of liquid detergents (plastics)

DMP criteria		Packaging of liquid detergents (plastics)
Data summary		Process information for LCA analysis and stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Processing information, materials (input, output, raw materials), processing parameters and settings, energy consumption shared in LCA analysis, and D2.6 "Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS" and internal project documents

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	N/A
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	
	Increase data RE-USE	
Allocations of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.	
Data security	Non-open research data	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)	
Other	N/A	

6.4 WP4 - Demo Case B. Creation of innovative formats and testing materials that improve recyclability and the end-of-life scenario.

6.4.1 Results of sorting tests of bio-based multimaterial packaging

DMP criteria		Results of sorting tests of bio-based multimaterial packaging
Data summary		Processes information of stages involved in demo cases
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Results of sorting tests of multimaterial packaging according to three established scenarios. Each scenario corresponds to 3, 5 and 10% (percentage of total) of bioplastic multimaterial referring respectively to current, near future and further future scenarios. Keywords: bioplastics, multimaterial, sorting tests
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	
	Increase data RE-USE	
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other	N/A

6.4.2 Results of sorting tests of bio-based packaging

DMP criteria		Results of sorting tests of bio-based packaging
Data summary		Processes information
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Results of sorting tests of bio-based CIRC-PACK packaging (bottles, trays and shopping bags) according to three established scenarios. Each scenario corresponds to 3, 10 and 15% (percentage of total) of bio-based packaging referring respectively to current, near future and further future scenarios. No difference between multi-layer and single-layer tray for practical implementation reasons. Keywords: bio-based packaging, sorting tests
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	
	Increase data RE-USE	
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.4.3 Spectral data of bio-based multimaterial packaging

DMP criteria		Spectral data of bio-based multimaterial packaging
Data summary		Sensor data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Extracted spectral data of bio-based multimaterial packaging using hyperspectral camera. First 224 columns of CSV file correspond to different wavelengths between 1000 and 1700 nanometers. Last column correspond to the label used for each sample (row). Number of rows corresponds to the numbers of samples. Keywords: bio-based multimaterial, hyperspectral, csv
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	
	Increase data RE-USE	
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

Data security	Non-open research data
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other	N/A

6.4.4 Spectral data of bio-based packaging

DMP criteria		Spectral data of bio-based packaging
Data summary		Sensor data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Extracted spectral data of bio-based CIRC-PACK packaging (bottles, trays and shopping bags). First 224 columns of CSV file correspond to different wavelengths between 1000 and 1700 nanometers. Last column correspond to the label used for each sample (row). Number of rows corresponds to the numbers of samples. Keywords: bio-based packaging, hyperspectral, csv, multi-layer, single-layer
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	
	Increase data RE-USE	
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.4.5 Packaging of powder detergent (multimaterial box)

DMP criteria		Packaging of powder detergent (multimaterial box)
Data summary		Laboratory and process information for stages involved in demo case B
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Processing information, materials (input, output, raw materials), processing parameters and settings, energy consumption shared in LCA analysis, Technical report RP1 and RP2 and deliverables
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	
	Increase data RE-USE	N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

Allocations of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	Non-open research data
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other	N/A

6.5 WP5 - Demo Case C. Creation of an effective after-use plastic economy by means of multisectorial cascaded approaching, adapting sorting technologies and in-line monitoring system

6.5.1 Automatic extrusion software for recycling materials

DMP criteria		Automatic extrusion software for recycling materials
Data summary		Sensors data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Before starting the trial, some data must be introduced into the programme by the operator; Internal project number_Date_Material. In addition, starting exact time of the trial is filled automatically. In order to find the data relevant to the project, the first raw search is done by the project number, in order to have a more precise search the name of the material must be introduced
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	There is not public access for these data. It is necessary access to the partner (AITIIP) servers
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	All different equipment in AITIIP are suffering the same digitalization programme in order to share the same data structure. Data is saved in a xlsx format easily to convert to other formats and quickly to open in different equipment.
	Increase data RE-USE	Data will be re-use in a future as a part of a more complex digital solutions involving all the steps of the value chain. Thus, all the partners involved in this WP has followed the data management criteria
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP5 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.5.2 Tensile values of recycled materials

DMP criteria		Tensile values of recycled materials
Data summary		Sensors data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Before starting the trial, some data must be introduced into the programme by the operator; Internal project number_Date_Material. In addition, starting exact time of the trial is filled automatically. In order to find the data relevant to the project, the first raw search is done by the project number, in order to have a more precise search the name of the material must be introduced
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	There is not public access for these data. It is necessary access to the partner (AITIIP) servers
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	All different equipment in AITIIP are suffering the same digitalization programme in order to share the same data structure. Data is saved in a xlsx format easily to convert to other formats and quickly to open in different equipment
	Increase data RE-USE	Data will be re-use in a future as a part of a more complex digital solutions involving all the steps of the value chain. Thus, all the partners involved in this WP has followed the data management criteria.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP5 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.5.3 Recycling process for biomaterials

DMP criteria		Recycling process for biomaterials
Data summary		Sensors data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Before starting the trial, some data must be introduced into the programme by the operator; Internal project number_Date_Material. In addition, starting exact time of the trial is filled automatically. In order to find the data relevant to the project, the first raw search is done by the project number, in order to have a more precise search the name of the material must be introduced
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	There is not public access for these data. It is necessary access to the partner (MI-PLAST) servers

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

	Making data INTEROPERABLE	All different equipment in MI-PLAST are suffering the same digitalization programme in order to share the same data structure. Data is saved in a xlsx format easily to convert to other formats and quickly to open in different equipment
	Increase data RE-USE	Data will be re-use in a future as a part of a more complex digital solutions involving all the steps of the value chain. Thus, all the partners involved in this WP has followed the data management criteria
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP5 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.5.4 Recycling methodology for automotive sector and possible adaptation and upgrade of the technology

DMP criteria		Recycling methodology for automotive sector and possible adaptation and upgrade of the technology
Data summary		Sensors data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Before starting the trial, some data must be introduced into the programme by the operator; Internal project number_ Date_Material. In addition, starting exact time of the trial is filled automatically. In order to find the data relevant to the project, the first raw search is done by the project number, in order to have a more precise search the name of the material must be introduced
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	There is not public access for these data. It is necessary access to the partner (CRF)servers
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	All different equipment in CRF are suffering the same digitalization programme in order to share the same data structure. Data is saved in a xlsx format easily to convert to other formats and quickly to open in different equipment
	Increase data RE-USE	Data will be re-use in a future as a part of a more complex digital solutions involving all the steps of the value chain. Thus, all the partners involved in this WP has followed the data management criteria
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP5 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other	N/A

6.5.5 Recycling methodology for absorbent hygienic products (AHP), possible adaptation and upgrade of the technology

DMP criteria		Recycling methodology for absorbent hygienic products (AHP), possible adaptation and upgrade of the technology
Data summary		Sensors data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	Before starting the trial, some data must be introduced into the programme by the operator; Internal project number_Date_Material. In addition, starting exact time of the trial is filled automatically. In order to find the data relevant to the project, the first raw search is done by the project number, in order to have a more precise search the name of the material must be introduced
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	There is not public access for these data. It is necessary access to the partner (FATER) servers
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	All different equipment in FATER are suffering the same digitalization programme in order to share the same data structure. Data is saved in a xlsx format easily to convert to other formats and quickly to open in different equipment
	Increase data RE-USE	Data will be re-use in a future as a part of a more complex digital solutions involving all the steps of the value chain. Thus, all the partners involved in this WP has followed the data management criteria
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP5 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.6 WP6 - Cross Sectorial Validation, Replicability and Upscaling of Solutions

6.6.1 Sorting Plants Rejections (not including the bulky items)

DMP criteria		Sorting Plants Rejections (not including the bulky items)
Data summary		Derived data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This dataset includes the data of the 3 sets of characterizations done during the task 6.1. Data has been collected in different sorting plants of Spain.
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	The name and location of the plants has been hidden to avoid comparison among plants. Each set of characterisations has measured different aspects of the rejected fractions of the plants included thins and end-of-line.
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	Results are anonymously published in D6.1. (public).
	Increase data RE-USE	Outcomes can be useful for the development of policies or the development of new packaging following eco-design recommendation in terms of waste prevention.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP6 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Open Research Data
Ethical aspects		N/A
Other		Uploaded into the open digital repository ZENODO by CIRCE

6.6.2 Online survey results

DMP criteria		Online survey results
Data summary		End-user personal data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This dataset includes .pdf questionnaires obtained from an online survey (EU Survey tool). Data were collected from September to December 2019 in the frame of task 6.3 activities
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	The survey aimed to draft a set of policy recommendations for EU institutions about circular economy in the plastic packaging sector.
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	Results are anonymously published in D6.6 (public)

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

	Increase data RE-USE	Outcomes can be useful for the development of policies or the creation of policy-based scenarios. However, the data will be available only to the owner of CIRC-PACK results
	Allocations of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP6 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
	Data security	Non-open research data
	Ethical aspects	Questionnaire results are anonymous in order to avoid the sharing of personal opinions. Participants willing to disclose their data with RINA-C indicated them into the questionnaire itself. However, RINA-C, have not disclosed these data into the deliverable, as agreed at the beginning of the activity. Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
	Other	N/A

6.7 WP7 - Exploitation, market analysis and business plan

6.7.1 Citizens' survey

DMP criteria		Citizens' survey
Data summary		End-user personal data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This dataset includes almost 10.000 answers obtained from self-administered paper questionnaires distributed in 2017 among Spanish, Italian, Belgian, Portuguese participants as well as information collected by computed assisted personal interviews in Kartal and Croatia in 2017.
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	This survey studied respondents' environmental profiles as well as their opinion regarding different product packaging, plastic bags and plastic waste recycling. Potential behaviour regarding new plastic materials, such as bio-based, recycled or biodegradable, were also checked. Main conclusions were published in autumn 2018 on magazine articles of the four consumers' organizations participating on this task (OCU, Altroconsumo, Deco Proteste and Test Achats) as well as CIRC-PACK deliverables 2.3 and 7.9. A video and several dissemination actions were carried out.
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	Outcomes were considered during stakeholders' discussions as well as project partners involved in demo case developments to help CIRC-PACK innovations to address consumers' sustainability needs.

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
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	Increase data RE-USE	Consumers behaviour and expectations collected is useful information for future outputs as plastics and waste management were a priority issue to be tackled by all stakeholders (Public Administrations, business and citizens)
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP7 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.7.2 Online survey

DMP criteria		Online survey
Data summary		End-user personal data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This dataset includes 4.896 answers obtained from an online survey conducted simultaneously in Spain, Italy, Belgium, Portugal, Croatia and Turkey (4.267 valid questionnaires) and a specific section for Kartal with 269 answers (243 online answers and 26 paper-based). Data were collected in January 2020
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	The survey aimed to seek out the most promising innovative proposals to become a successful marketed product and the advantages and constraints from a social approach. Three main topics were consulted: willingness to buy more sustainable grocery products, information needed on bioplastic products and waste management for new compostable products
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This survey was part of deliverable 7.9 Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers and final outcomes of the project. OCU also published a final article in Compra Maestra magazine of June 2020
	Increase data RE-USE	Outcomes can be useful for new plastic product developments as the survey identified some information and pricing constraints that remains similar in all new plastic products. Furthermore, participants declared a clear preference about possible economic policies to boost citizen collaboration with current waste management systems
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP7 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other	N/A

6.7.3 Validation of prototypes with real consumers

DMP criteria		Validation of prototypes with real consumers
Data summary		End-user personal data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This dataset includes 180 answers obtained from face-to-face interviews carried out in six cities Madrid (Spain), Lisbon (Portugal), Milan (Italy), Brussels (Belgium), Rijeka (Croatia) and Kartal (Turkey) during May-June 2019. The test was performed as a "hall test" and answers were collected by using tablets. The test consisted of a comparison of traditional packaging with a consolidated prototype of 7 products: fresh product tray, coffee capsule, bottle of shampoo, single-use and multiple-use bags, box of powder detergent and packaging of feminine pads.
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	Main conclusions were published in autumn 2019 on magazine articles of the four consumers' organizations participating on this task (OCU, Altroconsumo, Deco Proteste and Test Achats) as well as CIRC-PACK deliverable 7.9. A video and several information actions helped the dissemination.
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	The survey provided valuable insights that were included in final product developments, i.e. lack of resistance of food trays or too easiness to open the new box of powder detergent.
	Increase data RE-USE	The testing process is not commonly used but very useful for checking whether new product development will be noticed and appreciated by citizens. Some conclusions could be useful for other products or situations.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP7 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRCE-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.8 WP8 - Awareness, dissemination, communication

6.8.1 CIRCE-PACK Communication activities reported by partners

DMP criteria		CIRCE-PACK Communication activities reported by partners
Data summary		Project management data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This dataset includes 255 activities reported as communication and dissemination activities in the CIRCE-PACK project up until June 30 th , 2020.
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	CIRCE-PACK partners were asked to report all communication and dissemination activities in which they were taking part as to promote the CIRCE-PACK project and the results thereof. ICLEI Europe also reported activities through the tool in cases where partners shared the information through other channels. The data were used to produce the CIRCE-PACK Deliverable 8.4 in June 2020 and to report Dissemination and Communication figures to the European Commission through the Participant portal in June 2020 too.
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	the data was considered project partner meetings to assess the communications developments of CIRCE-PACK and help partners address potential shortcomings.
	Increase data RE-USE	Data collected is useful to make rough estimates for the communication activities of the entire Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP8 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRCE-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

6.8.2 Website Statistics from CIRCPACK

DMP criteria		Website Statistics from CIRCPACK
Data summary		Project management data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This dataset includes the number of unique visitors and the total downloads from the CIRCE-PACK Project until May 2020.
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	The Data informed on the use of the CIRCE-PACK Website
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This Dataset was used for Deliverable 8.4 in the CIRCE-PACK projects as well as to report Dissemination and Communication Numbers to the European Commission.
	Increase data RE-USE	Data collected is useful to make rough estimates for the communication activities of the entire Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme.
Allocations of resources		Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP8 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security		Non-open research data
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other		N/A

6.8.3 Twitter Impressions for @CIRC_Economy

DMP criteria		Twitter Impressions for @CIRC_Economy
Data summary		Project management data
FAIR data	Making data FINDABLE (including provisions of metadata)	This dataset includes the number of impressions for the Twitter profile CIRC_ECONOMY from CIRCE-PACK Project until May 2020.
	Making data openly ACCESSIBLE	The Data informed on the success of the CIRCE-PACK Social Media activity.
	Making data INTEROPERABLE	This Dataset was used for Deliverable 8.4 in the CIRCE-PACK projects as well as to report Dissemination and Communication Numbers to the European Commission.
	Increase data RE-USE	Data collected is useful to make rough estimates for the communication activities of the entire Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme.

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

Allocations of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP8 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	Non-open research data
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC)
Other	N/A

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

7 TIMETABLE FOR UPDATES

Data Management Plan was reviewed during project execution after each Steering Committee meeting. Steering Committee calendar was:

Meeting	Month	Dates	Country	Host Partner
I SC	month 7	16-17 November 2017	Italy	RINA
I GA, II SC	month 13	22 May 2018	Italy	NOVAMONT
III SC	month 19	30-31 October 2018	The Netherlands	BUMAGA BV
II GA, IV SC	month 25	15-16 May 2019	Spain	AITIIP
V SC	month 31	26 November 2019	Croatia	MI-PLAST
III GA, VI SC, Final meeting	month 36	21 April 2020	online	CIRCE

	Document:	D1.3 Data Management Plan		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRCE-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

8 CONCLUSIONS

This final version of CIRCE-PACK data management plan reflects the updated procedures that were implemented by the CIRCE-PACK project to efficiently manage the data produced. In particular, the final DMP anticipates the data management strategy regarding the collection, management, sharing, archiving and preservation of data.

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	Author:	CIRCE	Version	1
	Reference:	D1.3 CIRCE-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	29/6/20

9 REFERENCES

- European Commission, H2020 online manual, Data Management. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm
- Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, Version 3.0, 26 July 2016. http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf
- Metadata Standards Directory. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/metadata-standards-directory>
- How to create a Data Management Plan. OpenAIRE [Internet]. <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-create-a-data-management-plan>
- Zenodo platform. <http://www.zenodo.org>
- Wilkinson, M.D. et al., 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3, p.160018.
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
- Free webinar by Europa Media Trainings. Guidelines for data management – Expert Insights, May 2020.
- CIRCE-PACK project Deliverable D1.2 – Data Management Plan – first version, October 2017.